

Sexual and Reproductive Health Glossary

TRANSLATED INTO DARI

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ENGLISH MEDICAL TERM	DARI MEDICAL TERM	COLLOQUIAL EXPRESSIONS
<p>Abdominal ultrasound</p> <p>A type of imaging test to look at organs in the abdomen. A gel is applied to the skin over the abdomen before a handheld probe is gently pressed against the skin. The ultrasound machine sends out sound waves that reflect off body structures to create a picture.</p>	التراسوند بطنی	معاینه تلویزیونی
<p>Abortion (termination of pregnancy)</p> <p>A method to end a pregnancy. A medication abortion uses medicines to end the pregnancy. A procedural abortion uses a medical procedure to remove the pregnancy from the uterus.</p>	سقط جنین (پایان دادن به حاملگی)	ضایع کردن طفل
<p>Abstinence</p> <p>Not having sex.</p>	پرهیز از رابطه جنسی	
<p>Amniocentesis (amniotic fluid test)</p> <p>A test done during pregnancy to diagnose certain conditions in an unborn baby. The provider will insert a thin needle into the abdomen and withdraw a small amount of amniotic fluid.</p>	امنیوسنتیزس (نمونه گرفتن از کیسه امنیوتیک)	
<p>Amniotic fluid</p> <p>The fluid that surrounds the unborn baby during pregnancy.</p>	مایع امنیوتیک	
<p>Amniotic sac</p> <p>The fluid-filled structure inside the uterus that holds the amniotic fluid. The amniotic sac cushions and protects the developing baby</p>	کیسه امنیوتیک	
<p>Anemia</p> <p>A condition in which the blood does not carry enough oxygen to the rest of the body. Anemia can make a person feel tired, weak, and/or dizzy.</p>	کم خونی	

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<p>Anus</p> <p>The end of the digestive track where stool comes out of the body.</p>	مقعد	
<p>Areola</p> <p>The darker skin around the nipple.</p>	اریولا (هاله)	سیاهی اطراف نوک سینه
<p>Assisted vaginal delivery</p> <p>The use of medical tools to help guide a baby's head out of the vagina.</p>	ولادت کمکی از راه مهبل	
<p>Auscultation</p> <p>The action of listening to the sounds of the body (heart, lungs, or other organs). Auscultation is usually done using a tool called a stethoscope.</p>	سمع	گوش کردن آواز قلب طفل از بیرون
<p>Autonomy</p> <p>A patient's right to make decisions about their medical care without others trying to influence their decision.</p>	خودمختار	
<p>Barrier method</p> <p>Birth control that stops sperm from entering the vagina. Examples include: condoms, diaphragms, cervical caps, and contraceptive sponges.</p>	روش ایجاد مانعه	
<p>Benign</p> <p>Not cancer.</p>	سلیم	
<p>Biopsy</p> <p>The removal of cells or tissue for laboratory examination under a microscope.</p>	بیوپسی	نمونه گرفتن از قسمت از وجود برای معاینه

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<p>Birth control implant (contraceptive implant)</p> <p>A small, thin, flexible, rod inserted under the skin of the upper arm. The implant releases hormones that prevent pregnancy.</p>	امپلانت ضد حاملگی (روش جلوگیری از حمل از طریق امپلانت)	
<p>Birth control injection</p> <p>A shot of medication that prevents pregnancy. Pregnancy is prevented because eggs are not released from the ovaries.</p>	پیچکاری ضد حاملگی	
<p>Birth control patch</p> <p>A skin patch worn on the lower abdomen, buttocks, or upper body. The patch releases a medication absorbed through the skin that prevents pregnancy.</p>	پیچ ضد حاملگی	پلاستر ضد حاملگی
<p>Birth control ring</p> <p>A small flexible ring placed in the vagina. The ring releases a medication that prevents pregnancy.</p>	حلقه ضد حاملگی	
<p>Birth plan</p> <p>A written outline of what one would like to happen to support their health and experience during labor and delivery.</p>	پلان ولادت	
<p>Birth spacing (pregnancy spacing)</p> <p>The time from one child's birth until the next pregnancy.</p>	فاصله میان ولادت	
<p>Bladder</p> <p>A hollow, muscular organ in which urine is stored.</p>	مثانه	
<p>Blood transfusion</p> <p>When blood from one person is given to another person through a tube placed in the vein. The blood is first sterilized.</p>	تزریق خون	

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<p>Braxton-Hicks contractions (false labor pains)</p> <p>Irregular, mildly uncomfortable contractions of the uterus that occur during pregnancy.</p>	انقباضات براکستون-هیکس (دردهای مصنوعی ولادت)	
<p>Breast</p> <p>Glandular organs located on the chest. Breast tissue contains the glands that make milk.</p>	سینه	
<p>Breast cancer (malignancy)</p> <p>Cancer that forms in tissues of the breast.</p>	سرطان سینه (مالیگنسی)	
<p>Breast self-exam</p> <p>The process of checking one's breasts for lumps or other changes. Breast self-exams can help a person learn how their breasts normally look and feel and notice when changes occur.</p>	معاینه-خودی سینه	
<p>Breastfeeding</p> <p>The act of feeding breast milk to an infant. Babies can be fed directly from the breast, or breast milk can be pumped and then fed to the baby from a bottle. Milk can be pumped by hand with a manual (hand-powered) pump or with an electric pump.</p>	تغذیه با شیر مادر	
<p>Breech presentation</p> <p>The baby is positioned for delivery with the buttocks or feet first rather than the head.</p>	بریچ (طفل که به پای باشد)	
<p>Cervical cancer</p> <p>Cancer that forms in tissues of the cervix.</p>	سرطان عنق رحم	
<p>Cervix</p> <p>The opening between the vagina and the uterus.</p>	عنق رحم	

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<p>Cesarean delivery (c-section)</p> <p>Delivery of a baby from the uterus through a cut or incision made in the abdomen.</p>	سزارین (ولادت از راه بطن)	حمل به واسطه عملیات
<p>Circumcision</p> <p>The surgical removal of the foreskin that covers the head of the penis.</p>	ختنه کردن	
<p>Clinical breast exam</p> <p>A physical exam of the breast performed by a doctor to check for lumps or other changes.</p>	معاینه کلینیکی سینه	
<p>Colostrum</p> <p>The fluid that comes out of the breasts at the beginning of milk production.</p>	فله/آغوز	
<p>Colposcopy</p> <p>A procedure to examine the cervix and vagina. A vinegar solution may be used to make abnormal tissue easier to see. If abnormalities are seen, a biopsy may be taken.</p>	کولپوسکوپی	معاینه عنق رحم به واسطه آله طبی
<p>Congenital</p> <p>A condition that a person has from birth.</p>	مادرزادی	
<p>Consent</p> <p>An agreement between people to engage in sexual activity.</p>	رضایت	
<p>Constipation</p> <p>A condition, characterized by infrequent bowel movement, in which stool becomes hard, dry, and difficult to pass.</p>	قبضیت	

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<p>Contraception (birth control)</p> <p>Devices or medications used to prevent pregnancy.</p>	پیشگیری از حاملگی (کنترول حاملگی)	
<p>Deep vein thrombosis</p> <p>A condition in which a blood clot forms in one or more of the deep veins in the body, usually the legs.</p>	ترومبوسس سیاهرگ عمقی (علقه شدن خون در داخل رگ ها)	علقه شدن خون در داخل رگ ها
<p>Diagnostic tests</p> <p>Tests that look for a disease or cause of a disease in people with symptoms.</p>	معاینات تشخیصیه	
<p>Diaphragm (cervical cap)</p> <p>A bendable cup placed inside the vagina to cover the cervix and prevent pregnancy as a barrier method of contraception.</p>	دیافراگم (کلاهک عنق رحم)	
<p>Dilation</p> <p>The opening of the cervix. This occurs as labor nears.</p>	باز شدن عمق رحم	
<p>Dilation and Curettage</p> <p>A procedure to remove tissue from inside the uterus. A D&C may be used to clear the uterine lining after a miscarriage or abortion.</p>	باز شدن عمق رحم و کورتاژ	
<p>Eclampsia</p> <p>The new onset of seizures occurring in pregnancy or after pregnancy that are linked to high blood pressure. People with eclampsia may also have damage to other body organs.</p>	ایکلمپسی	فشار بلند و حملات اختلاجی در جریان حمل
<p>Ectopic pregnancy</p> <p>A pregnancy in a place other than the uterus, usually in one of the fallopian tubes.</p>	حاملگی خارج از رحم	

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<p>Ejaculation</p> <p>The discharge of semen from the tip of the penis.</p>	انزال شدن	
<p>Emergency oral contraception</p> <p>Method used to prevent pregnancy after unprotected sexual intercourse.</p>	ادويه فمی جلوگیری از حمل	
<p>Endometrium</p> <p>The lining of the uterus.</p>	اندومتر	قسمت درونی رحم
<p>Epidural block</p> <p>A type of pain medication that is injected into the space around the spinal nerves.</p>	پیچکاری بی حسی	پیچکاری کرختی
<p>Episiotomy</p> <p>A surgical cut made in the area between the vagina and the anus to widen the vaginal opening for delivery.</p>	برش جراحی ناحیه پرینه	اپیزیوتومی (برش جراحی ناحیه پرینه)
<p>External Cephalic Version (ECV)</p> <p>A technique in which the doctor attempts to manually move a baby in breech position into the head-down position.</p>	برابر کردن سر طفل به عنق رحم	
<p>External condom</p> <p>A thin pouch that keeps sperm from entering the vagina. External condoms are worn on the penis. Condoms are used during sex to prevent sexually transmitted infections and pregnancy.</p>	کاندوم	
<p>Fallopian tubes</p> <p>Muscular tubes that connect the ovaries to the uterus. Fertilization of an egg usually takes place in a fallopian tube.</p>	لوله های فالوپ/نفیرها	

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<p>Family planning</p> <p>The information, means and methods that allow individuals and families to decide if and when to have children.</p>	تنظیم خانواده	فاصله میان ولادت
<p>Fertility awareness (natural family planning) method</p> <p>A set of practices to track a person's natural body functioning to determine when they are most likely to get pregnant.</p>	روش آگاهی از حاملگی (تنظیم خانواده طبیعی)	
<p>Full-term</p> <p>A baby born on time, between 39 weeks and 42 weeks.</p>	بارس	تولد به وقت
<p>Gynecologist</p> <p>A doctor who specializes in women's reproductive health.</p>	متخصص نسایی	
<p>Hemorrhage</p> <p>Heavy bleeding.</p>	خونریزی شدید	
<p>Hemorrhoids</p> <p>Swollen blood vessels located in or around the anus.</p>	بواسیر	
<p>Hormones</p> <p>Chemicals made in the body that control the function of cells or organs.</p>	هورمون ها	
<p>Hysterectomy</p> <p>A surgery to remove the uterus.</p>	هیستریکتومی (برداشتن رحم)	بیرون کردن رحم به وسیله عملیات

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<p>Induction</p> <p>When a healthcare provider helps initiate or progress the childbirth process using medications or other medical techniques.</p>	سرعت دادن حمل به واسطه تخنیک طبی یا ادویه	
<p>Infertility</p> <p>When someone who wants to become pregnant does not become pregnant after having sex regularly. To be defined as infertility, you must have been trying to become pregnant for 1 year without using birth control.</p>	عقامت	بی اولادی
<p>Injection</p> <p>Use of a syringe and needle to push fluids or drugs into the body.</p>	تزریق ادویه	
<p>Internal condom</p> <p>A thin pouch that keeps sperm from entering the vagina. Internal condoms are inserted into the vagina. Condoms are used during sex to prevent sexually transmitted infections and pregnancy.</p>	کاندوم زنانه	
<p>Intimate partner violence</p> <p>The use of physical, sexual, or emotional threats or actions against a romantic partner. This includes non-consensual sex, being hit or kicked, and more.</p>	خشونت از طرف همسر	
<p>Intrauterine device (IUD)</p> <p>A small device that is inserted and left inside the uterus to prevent pregnancy. Depending on the type of IUD, it can remain in place for 3, 5, or 10 years.</p>	آی-یو-دی (وسیله داخل رحمی)	لوپ
<p>Labor</p> <p>The tightening of the uterine muscles that cause the cervix to open, thin, and stretch. Labor allows for the baby to be born.</p>	درد ولادت	

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<p>Lactation</p> <p>The production of breast milk.</p>	شیردهی	
<p>Lactational Amenorrhea Method (LAM)</p> <p>A temporary method of birth control that is based on the natural way the body prevents the release of an egg when a person is exclusively breastfeeding. LAM is typically effective for up to 6 months postpartum if the menstrual period has not returned.</p>	جلوگیری از حمل به واسطه شیردهی	
<p>Long-acting hormonal method</p> <p>Birth control that lasts years after insertion or until the device is removed. Examples include: intrauterine devices or birth control implants.</p>	روش هورمونی طولانی مدت	روش جلوگیری از حمل به واسطه ادویه هورمونی طولانی مدت
<p>Mammogram</p> <p>An x-ray, a type of imaging test that takes pictures of bones and soft tissues of the breast to look for early signs of breast cancer.</p>	ماموگرام	معاینه سینه به واسطه اکس-ری
<p>Mastectomy</p> <p>Surgery to remove part or all of the breast as a way to treat or prevent breast cancer.</p>	ماستکتومی (برداشتن سینه)	
<p>Mastitis</p> <p>An inflammation of the breast tissue, sometimes due to an infection. Mastitis is most common during breastfeeding.</p>	ماستاییتس (التهاب سینه)	
<p>Menopause</p> <p>The time when a person's menstrual periods stop permanently. Menopause is confirmed 12 months after their last period.</p>	قطع عادت ماهوار	

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<p>Menstruation (period)</p> <p>The regularly monthly shedding of blood and tissue from the uterus that happens when a person is not pregnant.</p>	عادت ماهوار	
<p>Miscarriage (spontaneous abortion)</p> <p>The unexpected or spontaneous loss of a uterine pregnancy before 20 weeks.</p>	سقط جنین (سقط خود به خودی)	نقصان
<p>Nausea and vomiting in pregnancy (morning sickness)</p> <p>Feel like throwing up, and throwing up, that occurs during early pregnancy.</p>	تهوع و استفراغ در دوران حاملگی (مریضی صبحگاهی)	دلبدی
<p>Neonatologist</p> <p>A doctor who specializes in the care of premature babies or newborns with complex health conditions.</p>	متخصص نوزادان	
<p>Obstetrician</p> <p>A doctor who provides care during pregnancy and delivers babies.</p>	متخصص ولادی	
<p>Oral contraception</p> <p>Medications, specifically pills, used to prevent pregnancy or to decrease monthly bleeding and pain caused by the menstrual cycle.</p>	ادویه فمی پیشگیری از حمل	
<p>Osteoporosis</p> <p>A condition in which bones thin and become weak, allowing them to break more easily.</p>	پوکی استخوان	
<p>Ovarian cancer</p> <p>Cancer that forms in tissues of the ovary.</p>	سرطان تخمدان	

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<p>Ovarian cyst</p> <p>Sacs, usually filled with fluid, in or on the surface of an ovary. Most ovarian cysts are harmless and will go away on their own. Sometimes ovarian cysts can become twisted or rupture requiring immediate surgical removal.</p>	کیست تخمدان	
<p>Pap smear (Papanicolaou test)</p> <p>A procedure to test for cervical cancer or cell changes that may lead to cervical cancer. A tool called a speculum is used to look inside the vagina and a small brush is used to gently remove cells from the surface of the cervix and the area around it so they can be checked.</p>	پاپ اسمیر (معاینه پاپانیکولا)	
<p>Pediatrician</p> <p>A doctor who cares for infants, children, and young adults.</p>	متخصص اطفال	
<p>Pelvic exam</p> <p>An internal and external physical exam of the pelvic organs including the vagina, cervix, uterus, fallopian tubes, and ovaries.</p>	معاینه لگن خاصره	
<p>Perinatal</p> <p>The time before and immediately after birth. Typically lasts from 20-22 weeks gestation and 1-4 weeks after birth.</p>	زمان قبل و بعد از ولادت	
<p>Perineal tear</p> <p>An injury to the tissue between the vagina and the anus. A perineal tear can happen during a vaginal delivery and will be repaired by a doctor.</p>	پاره شدن مهبل به طرف مقعد	
<p>Perineum</p> <p>The area between the vagina and the anus.</p>	پرینه	ناحیه حوصله

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<p>Placenta</p> <p>An organ that develops in the uterus during pregnancy and provides nutrients and oxygen to the developing baby. The placenta also removes waste from the baby's blood.</p>	پلاستنا	
<p>Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS)</p> <p>A very common condition caused by an imbalance of reproductive hormones. This imbalance can lead to cysts on the ovaries, menstrual problems, and difficulty becoming pregnant. PCOS is a treatable condition.</p>	سندروم تخمدان پولی کیستیک (PCOS)	
<p>Post-term</p> <p>A baby is born late, after 42 weeks.</p>	ولادت دیررس	
<p>Postpartum</p> <p>The weeks following the birth of a child.</p>	پس از ولادت	زچه گی
<p>Postpartum depression</p> <p>A type of depression that develops in the first year after the birth of a child. People with postpartum depression experience emotional high and lows, frequent crying, anxiety, and may have trouble caring for their baby. Postpartum depression is common and can be treated. Please talk to a health care professional.</p>	افسردگی بعد از ولادت	
<p>Pre-eclampsia</p> <p>A condition that occurs when a pregnant person has a high blood pressure. The high blood pressure can damage other parts of their body.</p>	پری-ایکلامپسی	اختلالات هنگام یا بعد از ولادت بخاطر بلند رفتن فشار خون
<p>Pre-term</p> <p>A baby is born early, before 37 weeks of pregnancy.</p>	ولادت قبل از وقت	

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ENGLISH MEDICAL TERM	DARI MEDICAL TERM	COLLOQUIAL EXPRESSIONS
<p>Pregnancy</p> <p>The state of carrying a developing baby within the uterus. Pregnancy usually lasts about 40 weeks.</p>	<p>حاملگی</p>	
<p>Prenatal care</p> <p>The prenatal period is the time during pregnancy and before birth. Prenatal care is the health care received by a pregnant person before they give birth.</p>	<p>مراقبت دوران حاملگی</p>	
<p>Prenatal vitamins</p> <p>Medication made for pregnant people that contain the vitamins and minerals needed during, before, and after pregnancy. These vitamins help support the baby's healthy growth and the pregnant person's health.</p>	<p>ویتامین های دوران حاملگی</p>	
<p>Primary care provider (PCP)</p> <p>A doctor or other licensed medical professional who manages a person's health care over time, most commonly in a clinic setting.</p>	<p>فراهم کننده خدمات اولیه (PCP)</p>	
<p>Quickening</p> <p>When a pregnant person first feels their baby move in their uterus.</p>	<p>تکان خوردن طفل در رحم</p>	
<p>Screening tests</p> <p>Tests that look for possible signs of disease in people who do not have symptoms.</p>	<p>سکریننگ</p>	
<p>Sexual agency</p> <p>The ability to identify, communicate, and negotiate one's sexual needs.</p>	<p>اختیار جنسی</p>	
<p>Sexual violence</p> <p>Sex acts or attempts that are forced on one person by another.</p>	<p>خشونت جنسی</p>	

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<p>Sexually transmitted infections (STIs)</p> <p>An infection that is spread by sexual contact.</p>	انتانات ساری جنسی (STIs)	
<p>Short-acting hormonal method</p> <p>Birth control that lasts days, weeks, or months. Examples include: birth control pills, vaginal rings, skin patches, or contraceptive injections.</p>	میتود هورمونی کوتاه-اثر	میتود کوتاه-اثر هورمونی جلوگیری از حمل
<p>Shoulder dystocia</p> <p>A condition that occurs when the one or both of a baby's shoulders get stuck when the baby is exiting the pelvis. Extra steps may be needed to deliver the baby.</p>	دیتوشی شانه (بند شدن شانه طفل در رحم مادر در هنگام ولادت)	
<p>Speculum</p> <p>A medical tool used to hold open the walls of the vagina for examination of the vagina and cervix.</p>	سپوکولوم (وسیله برای بازکردن مهبل جهت معاینه مهبل و عنق رحم)	
<p>Spermicide</p> <p>Chemicals, including creams, gels, foams, that stop sperm from moving. Spermicide is inserted into the vagina before sex and is used as method of birth control.</p>	مواد اسپرم کش	
<p>Still birth</p> <p>The death or loss of a baby after 20 weeks of pregnancy or during birth.</p>	به دنیا آمدن طفل مرده	
<p>Transvaginal ultrasound</p> <p>A type of imaging test to look at the uterus, ovaries, fallopian tubes, cervix, and pelvic area. A handheld probe will be gently placed inside the vagina. The ultrasound machine sends out sound waves that reflect off body structures to create a picture.</p>	التراسوند ترانس واژینال (معاینه تلویزیونی از راه مهبل)	

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<p>Trimesters</p> <p>A pregnancy is divided into three, three-month time periods.</p>	ترایمستر	
<p>Tubal ligation</p> <p>A form of permanent female birth control. Tubal ligation works by tying the fallopian tubes closed to prevent the passage of eggs from the ovaries to the uterus.</p>	بستن لوله (نفیر) های رحمی	
<p>Umbilical cord</p> <p>A tube-like structure that connects the unborn baby to the placenta. The umbilical cord delivers nutrients and oxygen and removes waste products.</p>	بند ناف	
<p>Unintended pregnancy</p> <p>A pregnancy that is unexpected or occurs without trying.</p>	حاملگی ناخواسته	
<p>Urethral catheter</p> <p>A tube used to drain urine from the bladder.</p>	پیپ مجرای ادرار	
<p>Urinary tract infection</p> <p>An infection in any part of the urinary system including the kidneys, ureters, bladder, and urethra. Symptoms may include pain or burning during urination, cloudy or bad-smelling urine, feeling a need to urinate often or right away, pain in the back or lower abdomen, fever, and vomiting.</p>	انتانات مجاری ادراری	
<p>Uterine contractions</p> <p>The tightening up of uterine muscles.</p>	انقباضات رحمی	درد های ولادت

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<p>Uterine prolapse</p> <p>A condition where the uterus move down from its normal position to press into or out of the vagina.</p>	پرولیپس رحم (برآمدن رحم از راه مهبل)	
<p>Uterus</p> <p>A muscular organ. During pregnancy, the uterus holds and nourishes the unborn baby.</p>	رحم	
<p>Vagina</p> <p>The internal passage leading from the cervix of the uterus to the opening of the body.</p>	مهبل	
<p>Vaginal discharge</p> <p>A clear or whitish fluid that comes out of the vagina. Discharge is normal, but changes in amount, thickness, color or smell could indicate an infection.</p>	ترشحات مهبل	
<p>Vasectomy</p> <p>A form of permanent male birth control. A vasectomy works by cutting the tubes that carry sperm out of the testicles.</p>	واژکتومی	بند نمودن لوله های سپرم مرد ها-طریقه جلوگیری از حمل
<p>Viable</p> <p>Ability of the unborn baby to live under normal conditions outside the uterus.</p>	ماندنی	
<p>Well-woman visit</p> <p>A yearly checkup with a healthcare provider that focuses on a woman's sexual, reproductive, and overall health. This may also be called an annual exam.</p>	معاینه صحتی سالانه	

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<p>Withdrawal method</p> <p>The process of removing the penis from the vagina to ejaculate outside the vagina. This method is less effective than other options of birth control and also does not protect against sexually transmitted infections.</p>	<p>میتود قطع مناسبات هنگام ارضای جنسی مرد یا خروج مایع منوی</p>	<p>احتیاط</p>
<p>Yeast infection</p> <p>Yeast is a fungus that can cause infection in the vagina, vulva and other parts of the body. This fungal infection can cause itching, burning or irritation.</p>	<p>فنگس مهبل</p>	

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